

USE OF CONCEPT MAPPING AS A PEDAGOGICAL TOOL TO FOSTER MEANINGFUL LEARNING IN MATHEMATICS AT THE MIDDLE EDUCATION STAGE

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ABSTRACT

As we know concept mapping is a cognitive tool that can present information to students in a visual form in a very effective and systematic manner. Meaningful learning is a process through which students can connect new information to old information in a meaningful way (Ausubel, 1967). Through concept mapping, when students see the content in different types of boxes and connect new information to old information through nodes, linking lines, cross-links, symbols, pictures, etc. it leads them to meaningful learning. When students learn new concepts through signs, symbols, pictures, etc. through concept mapping, they are involved in the process of mathematization (National Curriculum Framework-2005). If we refer to the documents of ASER-2021 and National Achievement Survey-2021, students experience more difficulty in learning mathematics as compared to other subjects at the elementary level. The National Education Policy 2020 has mentioned in its document that we need to use such new educational techniques at the elementary level through which the overall development of the students can be possible. In this direction, concept maps can play an important role at the middle educational level. For example, in this research paper, the researcher has tried to develop a small module (1 concept) with a combination of concept maps and constructivism. Through which an attempt has been made to explain how mathematics can be taught in a meaningful way through concept mapping at the middle educational level. This short module type has been developed by the researcher based on the 5E (Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, Evaluate) model of constructivism. Certainly, based on this brief module, a comprehensive module can be developed to teach mathematics to students at the middle educational level, which can enhance the meaningful learning of students in the subject of mathematics.

Key words: Concept Mapping, Meaningful Learning, Constructivism, Mathematics Education, Middle Education Stage.

INTRODUCTION

Although at the middle stage, many types of subjects like science, history, geography, etc. can be taught easily through the constructivist approach of concept mapping. But the researcher has chosen the subject of mathematics here because in the last few years Analyzing the National Achievement Survey and ASER report, we come to know that mathematics is a subject in which, compared to other school subjects, students are struggling a lot in achieving the learning outcomes prescribed for a class. There can be many reasons for this, but it has been mentioned in the National Curriculum Framework 2005 that instead of

children being able to solve as many mathematics problems as possible, teachers should use the constructivist approach to teach them and help in the Mathematization of students' thoughts. This simply means that students can think mathematically using signs, symbols, and logic to solve everyday tasks and problems inside and outside school.

We know that the nature of mathematics subject is quite different from other subjects, with the increase in the level of classes, students experience difficulty in thinking abstractly in the subject of mathematics and in understanding and solving mathematical problems. One of the main reasons for this is that even today the subject of mathematics is being taught with the help of chalk and board with traditional teaching methods. Therefore students are not actively involved in the learning process, do not participate in activities, avoid learning in groups, and get very few opportunities to present their views on any concept. Due to this they are not able to think in a new way about the problems of mathematics and are not able to present their possible solutions to their learning group and teacher in the class, due to which Mathematics becomes a boring subject for them.

The reality is that even today in a vast country like India, there is a huge shortage of middle-stage school teachers who have been trained to do teaching work through a constructivist approach. Apart from this, some other important reasons also come to light such as it has been seen many times that students form some negative prejudices towards the subject of mathematics from a young age. These prejudices develop within the students towards fear of mathematics, due to which students' interest towards mathematics subject reduces significantly and they do not enjoy solving the problems of mathematics subject. As a result, there is a negative impact on the achievement of students in mathematics subject.

Concept mapping is a cognitive tool that is used to organize information, knowledge and understanding, establish relationships between multiple pieces of information and understand, explain and present them in a meaningful way. This is a technique through which students can create their maximum understanding of a concept or topic in a visual form on a page or piece of paper and then discuss and evaluate it.

This is a technique in which students use their active mind throughout the task by drawing their own pictures or maps that reflect their understanding of a concept. This technique supports developing one's own understanding of a concept and understanding it in a meaningful way by opposing passive learning and rote methods in the classroom. In this review research, the researcher has tried to explain the usefulness of concept mapping technique for learning mathematics subject at middle stage by analyzing various types of research present in this field through constructivist approach.

CONSTRUCTIVIST APPROACH

Constructivist approach is based on that dimension of teaching and learning in which students try to build their own understanding of a concept by discussing and discussing with their classmates and teachers. They enjoy engaging in learning related activities and try to discover new information through these activities. They also refine their understanding of a concept by connecting new information to already known information and making meaningful connections between the two. In this process, they build their understanding by asking questions, doing it themselves, experiencing and evaluating already known information (Sharma and Sarita, 2018).

The world-famous Swiss psychologist Jean Piaget is considered to be the father of constructivist learning. He had a deep interest in child development and cognitive psychology. He criticized the claim that knowledge was in a static, passive and fixed form and supported the ideas of John Dewey, Lev Vygotsky and Bruner. He believed that Constructivism is a new

technique in which students develop their own understanding and refine their understanding by talking to each other and reconsidering the information they already know.

Psychologists who support constructivism believe that knowledge is not just an object that a teacher delivers to the students on their tables in the classroom (Sharma, 2014). According to Grebe & Grebe, 1998, constructivism encourages students to construct their understanding through their own personal experiences, using appropriate objects and tools, and by discussing and deliberating with other students.

Diagram 1: Uses of constructivist approach

Source: Authors

CONCEPT MAPPING

Concept mapping technique was first developed by Joseph D. Novak in 1972. Concept mapping is a technique by which we can represent our learned knowledge or understanding in the form of a picture and can also evaluate our understanding. Concept mapping serves as a cognitive tool that shows a meaningful relationship between previous information and new information. In fact, concept map is a great tool for knowledge display which is very useful for teachers as well as students. Teachers can use the concept map technique in various tasks like evaluating the understanding of students, planning the content as per the need of the class, planning examinations etc. At the same time, students use this technology to strengthen their understanding in different types of educational activities and in different contexts of learning and teaching.

In India, concept mapping techniques have been in use for the last two decades at different levels of education such as courses at graduate level and above, pre-service training programs and in-service training programmes. But the use of concept mapping technique in educational instruction at the middle stage is quite new. Therefore, this review article is an attempt to give birth to new possibilities in this direction.

Main Components of Concept Maps

In this review article, the concept mapping technique has been chosen for instruction at the middle stage under the constructivist approach, therefore it becomes necessary to discuss all

the aspects related to the concept mapping technique in detail so that it can be understood that mathematics Or how can a better concept map be made in any other subject? To make a good concept map of any subject matter or topic, it is necessary that we have knowledge of the main parts of the concept map, we know which small elements together take the shape of a concept map. Therefore, an attempt has been made to explain the main parts of a concept map and the functions of those parts in a sequential manner with the help of pictures below-

Nodes: Concept map is a knowledge graph in which the network between concepts is shown graphically. Networks contain nodes within themselves. A concept map can have many nodes (points/vertices) within which concepts are written. These concepts are written within many types of geometric shapes such as rectangle, square, circle. These are called nodes.

Diagram 2: nodes (points/vertices)

Source: Authors

Linking Verbs: Concept map shows the relationship between several concepts (which we also call nodes). We use links to show this relationship. To show the relationship between concepts, we use linking phrases such as gives, rise to, result in, links to, involves etc. Links between concepts can be unidirectional, bidirectional, or unidirectional.

Diagram 3: Linking Verbs

Source: Authors

Proposition: Proposition is a type of sentence which is about an object or event, sometimes it already exists while on many occasions it is spoken or made relative to the situation. In concept map, a proposition is a meaningful sentence that connects two or more nodes

connected by linking phrases. In simple language, propositions work to make the meaning of linking verbs more clear.

Diagram 4: Proposition

Source: Authors

Hierarchy: In a concept map, information is arranged in descending order of importance. Generally, the most important concept is placed at the top of the map and the less important concepts are arranged at the bottom. This sequence of organizing information can be organized in any order, horizontal or vertical. This order of organizing information is called hierarchy.

Diagram 5: Hierarchy

Source: Authors

TYPES OF FEW MAIN CONCEPT MAPS

At present, the use of concept mapping has increased significantly in school education. Not only is it being used at the secondary and higher secondary level, it is also being used at the

middle stage to encourage meaningful learning. Concept maps can be made in many ways according to the need and situation, but some of the major types of concept maps which are mainly used by students and teachers at the school level are written below –

- Spider concept map
- Flow-chart concept map
- Hierarchy Concept Map
- System concept map

Diagram 6: Some major types of concept mapping

Spider concept map

Spider map is a major type of concept mapping. In this type of concept map, the main or central concept remains in the middle of the map and other sub-concepts are connected around the main concepts in different directions by suitable linking lines. Spider map is also called multi flow map because the flow from main concepts to other sub-concepts can be in different directions. Spider map can also be understood from the Hindi word Makdi Jaal, the way the structure of the spider web is in different directions from the center, no fixed order or pattern of any kind is followed in it, some similar structure is called spider concept. There is also a map. Spider type concept map is shown in diagram 7.

Image 1: Spider Concept Map

Image Source: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Evaluation-of-Concept-Maps-related-to-Angle-ConceptTuluk/03d8ff3cfd8d93b52611f48f8d51429e34ce86b5/figure/3>

Flow chart concept map

Flow chart concept mapping is a good and simple means of displaying information in a linear manner. In this type of concept mapping, the flow of information from the main concept to other sub-concepts is linear. Figure 8 shows the flow chart concept map.

Image 2: Flow chart Concept Map

Image Source: <http://www.learnattic.com/arithmetics/number-system/>

Hierarchy Concept Map

In this type of concept mapping, important concepts are placed at the top and sub-concepts are placed below it in descending order. Fresher told in 1993 that many researchers keep the main concept at the top of the map, but in hierarchy map it is not necessary that the main concept is always kept at the top, while making the map, the main concept is also placed in the middle of the map. And from there, co-concepts can be shown in different directions by creating a hierarchy.

Image 3: Hierarchy Concept Map

Image Source:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242319692_CONCEPT_MAPPING_IN_MIDDLE_SCHOOL_MATHEMATICS/figures?lo=1

System concept map

System concept map is also used to organize information like flow chart concept map but in system concept map, information is input from one end while the results are organized in output from the other end. Figure 10 shows the system concept map.

Image 4: System Concept Map

Image Source: <http://montessorimuddle.org/wp-content/uploads/2011/08/Algebra-PreAlgebra-Map-6-Ch01-1.png>

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

According to Kim and Lee (2017), idea mapping can enhance middle school pupils' capacity for mathematical problem-solving. Students who create concept maps are better able to visualise alternative answers and deconstruct complex problems into simpler parts. Jonassen and Rohrer-Murphy (1999) suggests that concept maps' visual and hierarchical features can be customized to match each student's unique learning needs while also aiding in better retention of mathematical concepts. Caas et al. (2004) explicit in their work technology can be used to construct dynamic idea maps that can be tailored for each student, enabling personalised learning experiences, according to Caas et al. (2004). The focus of Subramaniam, K.'s research from 2019 is on the application of idea mapping to improve students' conceptual knowledge of algebra. According to the study, concept mapping is a useful technique for increasing students' understanding of and aptitude for using algebraic concepts. According to Kim, H., and Reeves, T. C. (2007), their work addresses the larger idea of cognitive tools, such as concept mapping, in the context of problem-solving and learning. It emphasises the function of idea maps in assisting the mental operations necessary for solving mathematical problems. Canas, A. J., Reiska, P., Åhlberg, M., Dalgarno, B., & Kalas, I. (2019) investigates the advantages of including dynamic concept mapping tools in a learning management system (LMS) for mathematics instruction. It explains how such integration might improve group projects and learners' interest in mathematics classes. Novak, J. D., and Canas, A. J. (2008) looked into how idea mapping affected students' attitudes and performance in a mathematics course. Students who utilised concept mapping as a learning aid had greater achievement and more favourable attitudes towards mathematics, according to the research. The fundamental work by Novak and Canas (2008) contains instructions on how to create and use idea maps as well as a thorough discussion of the theory underlying concept mapping. It emphasises the usefulness of concept maps as systems for classifying and linking mathematical ideas. Çakiroğlu and Öztürk (2015) undertook a study to find out how concept mapping affected the performance and attitudes of maths students. The study, which was released in *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practise*, offers insightful information regarding the potential advantages of idea mapping as a teaching tool. The results show that idea mapping improves students' academic performance as well as their attitudes towards the subject. This study adds to the growing corpus of research on cutting-edge teaching techniques and emphasises the value of idea mapping in mathematics instruction to improve students' learning opportunities and cultivate a more favourable attitude towards the subject. Kumud (2016) conducted a comparative study of traditional lecture method and concept map techniques was conducted on higher secondary level students in Physics subject. The findings of this research tell us that the group which was taught through concept map techniques recorded a positive jump in their achievement. Anamika (2016) did research on concept map cognitive skills and concept attainment for which they selected Chemistry subject and class 9 students. The results of this research show that concept map cognitive skills are helpful in concept attainment by students. Somers (2009) conducted a study on using concept maps to explore pre-service teachers' perceptions about teaching practices and reflective processes based on science content knowledge. The results of this research show that concept maps are helpful in demonstrating students' understanding and finding relationships between concepts. Other findings of the research show that the ability of concept maps to find relationships in visual form is helpful in increasing the understanding of the subject matter.

Uses of concept mapping in teaching-learning process

At present, concept mapping is being used widely in the form of constructivist approach or constructivist learning model. In what ways concept mapping technique is used or can be used in the teaching-learning process, they are written point wise below-

- To focus and control students' attention
- Students can visualize the concepts they have learned and then create them.
- To help students organize their ideas and discover new connections.

- In creating new ideas through brain storming.
- Finding connections between complex ideas.
- To understand one's own learning by depicting complex ideas through pictures or diagrams.
- Linking new and old ideas to promote learning.
- To evaluate your understanding of concepts and improve your understanding.
- In planning the content for the class room by teachers.
- To understand the depth of a concept.
- To find logical relationships between concepts.
- In selection of necessary material for teaching-learning.
- Sorting out concepts.
- To identify the wrong concepts understood by the students.
- To learn the content through meaningful learning.
- To generate insight in the creative structure of students.
- To conduct formative and summative assessment of students.
- Students share information and learning within their groups.
- To promote group communication.

How is teaching mathematics possible through concept mapping technique under constructivist approach at middle stage?

Mathematics subject can be taught in many ways through constructivist approach at middle stage, but in this review article the researcher has tried to explain and show how mathematics subject can be taught to students using concept mapping technique in constructivist approach. For this, the researcher has created a concise model using the 5-E model of the constructivist approach (Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate and Evaluation) and concept mapping technique. For this model, the researcher has selected the topic '**Numbers and their Types**' from the first chapter '**Rational Numbers**' of the mathematics subject textbook of **class-8th** so that it can be explained that the constructivist approach in studying mathematics at the middle stage. Under this, how the teaching-learning process can be conducted by using concept mapping technique.

This short module is divided into two main parts where the left side attempts to represent a possible interaction between the teacher and the students while the right side shows the activities taking place on the board based on the students' answers. A total of five stages of this brief module are based on the **5-E model of the constructivist approach**, in which students' interaction with the teacher and board activity are shown sequentially in each stage.

Use of concept mapping technique in learning mathematics under constructivist approach at the middle stage.

(Short module)

Class- 8

Subject: Mathematics

Lesson: Rational Numbers

Subtopic: Numbers and their types

Time: 60 minutes

Learning outcomes

While making the concept map and after making the concept map, the students should-

- Will be able to explain the concept of numbers
- Will be able to differentiate between different types of numbers
- Will be able to check your misconceptions related to numbers
- Will be able to create concept maps of different numbers to explain them.

Long term objectives

Understanding numbers and their types using concept mapping techniques

Prerequisite knowledge and practical requirements

Concepts: Students must have some knowledge of the concepts related to numbers learned in previous classes.

Skills: Students will have the skills to think and express their views on number concepts learned in previous classes.

Behavior: Students will become familiar with how to read alone, in groups of two students, and in groups of more than two students.

Necessary accessories

- Educational resources present in the classroom
- A copy or A4 sheet
- Pen or pencil to make concept maps

Step-1 Engage

- Based on the previous knowledge of the students, the teacher will ask some questions to the students so that what students already understand about the subject being taught can be understood.
- These questions will be asked from the daily experiences of the students and the classes they have passed.
- When the teacher asks questions to the students, he will start making a concept map on the right side of the board based on the answers he gets.

Possible questions

Question: How do you all count the things around you?

Question: Can any of you count and tell how many students are there in this class?

Question: You have used 1,2,3...etc. to count the students, what are these?

Question: You said these are numbers? Can any of you tell me what the numbers are called?

(Note: Teachers will choose the questions based on the school environment and mental condition of the students, their readiness in the class.)

As students continue to answer the questions asked, a concept map will take shape with the help of their answers. Which will help students to discover new relationships.

Concept map on the board for step: 1

Step-2 Explore

After the first stage, when it has become clear to the students what numbers are? What are the uses of numbers? Now the teacher has written some different numbers on the board which the students have read in the following classes. The teacher asks them to identify those numbers -

1, 2, 3, 4...

0, 1, 2, 3, 4...

-1, -2, -3, -4...

$\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{2}{3}$, $\frac{8}{9}$...

$-\frac{4}{5}$, $-\frac{12}{7}$...

- Some students answer while others sit silently and then the teacher asks, have you heard about natural numbers and whole numbers?
- Most of the students have heard these words before. Some students even recognize the numbers. Based on their responses, the teacher develops a concept map.
- The remaining students listen carefully to the entire incident and watch the concept map being drawn on the board.

Step-3 Explain

- After the discussion in Step 2 and understanding the concept map made on the board, students understand that numbers can mainly be natural, whole, integer or rational numbers.
- Students are also seeing these relationships of numbers being formed on the board, in such a situation the teacher will question the students-

Question: Can you guys tell the difference between natural and whole numbers?

- Students can easily tell the difference between written numbers by looking at them.
- While the teacher will try to explain some of the differences using appropriate examples.
- Teacher speaks to students What have you understood from numbers so far? How many main types are there? The teacher gives students some time to think about their answers.

- The teacher sees which students in the class are still having trouble understanding and asks them one by one to describe the concept map made on the board.

Concept map on the board for step: 3

Step-4 Elaboration

- Students will look carefully at the concept map on the board and try to find relationships between the numbers.
- After some time, the teacher will ask the students to find out the relationships between different types of numbers based on their new understanding.

Step-5 Evaluation

- The teacher instructs the students to draw on a paper sheet in the form of a concept map whatever you have understood in today's class. The teacher will also give sufficient time to the students for this, after which they will discuss the concept map made by the students.
- The students who have created all the types of numbers correctly through the concept map or the student whose concept map is most suitable should be made on the board and all the students will be asked to think about it so that the remaining students can revise their mistakes.

Note: This short module will be used to teach middle stage mathematics through concept mapping technique under constructivist approach. This module has been created to explain how mathematics can be taught using concept mapping technique under the constructivist approach at the primary level. This brief module has been created entirely on the basis of the researcher's own understanding and thoughts. At the middle stage, a detailed module can be created to teach different lessons in Mathematics using this method and changes can be made keeping in mind the needs of the students and depending on the teacher's proficiency in constructivist approach and concept mapping technique. The basic objective of developing this module is to demonstrate that mathematics subject at middle stage can be taught very efficiently through the combined use of constructivist approach and concept mapping technique which encourages innovation in mathematics subject at middle stage. And introduces middle stage teachers to a powerful teaching technique in the context of the National Education Policy-2020.

How can middle stage teachers use concept mapping technique under constructivist approach?

As mentioned in the National Curriculum Framework-2005 and National Education Policy-2020, we should take children towards new information or knowledge in such a way that they can make proper use of the knowledge they have already learned. Concept mapping is a technique through which students move towards discovering new knowledge by easily remembering previously learned concepts and making connections with new concepts. At the middle stage, teachers can use concept mapping technique under constructivist approach to teach new knowledge to students in a meaningful way during their teaching-learning in the following ways:

- Concept mapping technique is quite new to the students at middle stage so teachers should first teach the students what is concept mapping? Give them information about this topic and tell them what the main components of concept mapping are.
- How is a concept map made on a theme or topic? Prepare and present it in front of the students and motivate them to make this concept map again and also make them practice making concept maps on topics related to other mathematics lessons.
- Teachers should also tell students the benefits of understanding a subject matter through concept mapping and show them in visual form how a concept map connects different dimensions of information through linking lines. These types of activities encourage students to find connections between concepts and consider new relationships in which students actively seek out and understand new information.
- It is important for teachers to be aware of what students already know about a subject or concept. Or what kind of understanding do you have? If the teachers make a concept map from the students of the lessons taught in earlier classes, then the teachers will be able to know whether the students have understood those concepts properly or not or there is a need to give more practice to the students on the same topic.
- Concept maps made by students on the same subject are not the same, they are of different types because due to individual differences, the way of thinking of each student is different, and hence the teacher can improve the thinking of the students by using concept maps. By understanding the pattern, suitable teaching aids can be selected for them.
- At the middle stage, it is necessary that while understanding any concept, students should do divergent thinking on it, which is helpful in increasing the creativity skills within them. Concept map technique gives students enough time and opportunity to think divergently on any topic or concept. Provides which helps in developing the quality of divergent thinking within the students. Teachers should mention the concept map creatively made by a student to other students, show it to them and encourage them to make similar concept maps.

- Teachers can also use concept maps as class tests from time to time or as an assessment tool to assess a topic or concept after it has been explained in class and remedial classes can also be arranged for students who are having trouble understanding concepts.
- Teachers can also use concept mapping techniques to organize the content to be taught in the classroom and plan the use of supporting materials before entering a classroom.

CONCLUSION

Concept mapping is a technique that can be used in many ways in the teaching-learning process at the middle stage. Concept mapping technique can become a good medium to use the constructivist approach at a higher level because all the properties of concept mapping fulfill all the conditions required for the constructivist approach. For a long time in the past, it was believed that the concept mapping technique was not suitable for use in teaching-learning at the middle stage because a section of researchers did not believe that students of this age had the mental capacity to do so. Are not mature enough to adopt technology or teaching methodology.

But in the last two decades, many researches have been done in western countries using concept mapping technique at middle stage and surprisingly the results have been meaningful. In view of this sequence, in the last few years, NCERT has made some major changes in the text books at the middle stage and some special topics, or questions, have been given place in the middle and at the end of the lessons so that higher order thinking skills can be developed in the students. The C.B.S.E. and I.C.S.E. currently used concept maps are being used extensively in the middle stage textbooks of the board to make the content interesting and to explain new relationships easily. Which shows concept mapping acceptability at present at middle stage.

We know that concept map is a cognitive tool which is used for meaningful learning whereas constructivist approach is a teaching method through which students are taught to learn by doing. We know that concept map is a cognitive tool which is used for meaningful learning whereas constructivist approach is a teaching method through which it motivates students to learn by doing. But due to the nature of the subject of mathematics being quite different from other taught subjects, it is not possible to use the constructivist approach as widely as it is possible in other subjects, hence teaching mathematics through concept mapping technique under the constructivist approach.

Generally it is seen that concept mapping technique is used to develop higher order thinking skills in students. Major documents like National Curriculum Framework-2005 and National Education Policy-2020 have recommended that mathematics teaching at the primary level should be such that students get ample opportunities for exploration (discovery), and learning by doing so that students acquire new knowledge. While learning the concepts, you can also enjoy the learning process.

In this sequence, the use of concept mapping technique at the middle stage under the constructivist approach gives rise to a possibility through which students can truly get actively involved in the teaching-learning process and integrate new and old information as per their understanding. They make meaningful connections between them and develop their understanding by adopting new concepts on their own, i.e. by using the constructivist approach. In this review article, the researcher has explained with the help of a short module how the merits of constructivist approach and concept mapping technique can be taught to the students in a meaningful and interesting way at the middle stage. This research article will help students and teachers to adopt a new and easier teaching methodology in the coming times. This review research will definitely serve to provide a way for researchers doing research on innovation in the subject of mathematics in the coming times.

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